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Research Article

**OUTCOME OF THE TREATMENT OF BURKITT LYMPHOMA
AT KING ABDUL-AZIZ MEDICAL CITY, RIYADH****Mohsen Alzahrani¹, Abdulrahman Alhadlaq², Abdulrahman Alqahtani², Faisal Alnaqa²,
Khalid Alotaibi², Mohammed Alrashed², Muath Alghamdi*²**¹Oncology Department, King Abdullah Specialized Children Hospital, King Abdul-Aziz Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.,²College of Medicine, King Saud bin Abdul-Aziz University for Health Sciences, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:****Objective:** To study the response of patients of Burkitt lymphoma to the first line regimen at King Abdul-Aziz Medical City in Riyadh, and to determine the 2-years survival rate.**Methods:** A retrospective cross-sectional study was performed that included all patients diagnosed with Burkitt lymphoma from 1 January 2001 to 1 August 2017. SPSS version 20 software was used to analyze the data. The association between mortality rate and patients' characteristics, risk factors and complication was assessed. Fischer's exact test was used to detect significant values.**Results:** The study included thirteen adult patients with Burkitt lymphoma whom were treated with the first line regimen in King Abdul-Aziz Medical City, Riyadh. The variables that showed significant results were Bone marrow involvement with a P value of 0.014 and Tumor lysis syndrome with a P value of 0.045. Mortality rate in this study was 23% with fatalities occurred within the first two months of the treatment.**Conclusion:** Burkitt lymphoma is a disease of a good prognosis. The treatment regimen used for patients with Burkitt lymphoma in King Abdul-Aziz Medical City showed similar mortality rate as those recorded in other global studies. Tumor lysis syndrome and bone marrow involvement had a significant effect on mortality rate in this study.**Keywords:** Burkitt, Lymphoma, Outcome, Treatment**Corresponding author:****Muath Alghamdi,**Oncology Department, King Abdullah Specialized Children Hospital,
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INTRODUCTION:

Burkitt lymphoma (BL) is one of the subdivisions of non-hodgkin lymphoma. BL is defined as overexpression and deregulation of the c-MYC oncogene due to translocation of the immunoglobulin gene on chromosomes t(8,14).[1] There are three forms of Burkitt lymphoma sporadic, endemic, and immunodeficiency-associated. [2,3] They differ in their epidemiology, genetic features, and clinical presentation. However, they have similar clinical behavior and identical histological appearance. Each subtype of BL has a unique clinical feature. [2] The endemic (African) type presents in up to 60% of the cases as tumor in the jaw and facial bone. The sporadic type commonly effects the abdominal region with symptoms appearing as ascites, bowel obstruction, and gastrointestinal bleeding. The last form, the immunodeficiency-associated BL, involves lymph nodes, bone marrow, and the central nervous system in addition to the symptoms of which cause the immunodeficiency, such as, AIDS and Congenital immunodeficiency.[2,3] Patients with Burkitt lymphoma commonly present with a huge lymphadenopathy usually affecting the jaw.[1] Burkitt lymphoma has a good prognosis if patients presented early with chemotherapy being the essence of the treatment.[1,3] Multidrug combination of chemotherapy is used to treat this aggressive and rapid growing lymphoma.[1]

The outcome and treatment of Burkitt lymphoma have been studied in several countries. In one study [4], newly diagnosed children under age of 18 years with Burkitt lymphoma in Malawi were enrolled from June 2013 to May 2015. The treatment used was a six cycles of CHOP (cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, vincristine, prednisone). The sample size was 73 children with a mean age of 9.2, 48 of them were male. Sixteen percent had stage 1 or 2 disease, 49% had stage 3 and 29% had stage 4. The survival rate on an 18-month period was 29%. Compared to less intensive regimens in Malawi, COHP did not improve outcome in pediatrics with BL. Another study [5] was done on 8 HIV patients with Burkitt lymphoma between 25 and 43 years of age, 63% in stage 4. In this group the outcome of HIV patients treated by intensive chemotherapy was more effective with high cure rate and lower relapse rate. In an American study [6] that had been conducted on 54 BL patients, which followed the same approach of treatment in Africa, showed an overall two year survival rate of 54 percent. The results also showed similarity between American and African patients regarding to response rate, relapse frequency and survival. The studies mentioned were done globally, however there are insufficient local studies

about the line of treatments used in Saudi Arabia and their outcome.

There are insufficient epidemiological and treatment outcome studies about Burkitt Lymphoma in Saudi Arabia. This study is significant because it provides updated data about the patients treated in King Abdul-Aziz Medical City, Riyadh. The data in this research shows the response to the first line regimen, relapse frequency, and survival rate. However, the fact that Burkitt Lymphoma is an uncommon disease resulted in a small sample size in accordance with the many variables that we have which limited the research data. The research testifies the outcome of the treatment of Burkitt lymphoma in King Abdul-Aziz Medical City, Riyadh.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This was a retrospective cross-sectional study in which the main objective was to study the response to the first line therapy and to measure 2-year survival outcome in patients with Burkitt Lymphoma. The research included all patients diagnosed with Burkitt lymphoma in the last 15 years. We estimated around 3 to 4 cases diagnosed each year with Burkitt lymphoma at KAMC according to another local study done in King Abdul-Aziz Medical City, Riyadh (unpublished data). Based on the available sample of 50 patients, with response distribution of 50% and 95% confidence level, the margin of error will be 14%. The study was conducted in King Abdul-Aziz Medical City-Riyadh which is a tertiary care center. The lymphoma cases are diagnosed in the hospital by medical or surgical specialties and then referred to hematology. Also, some cases are accepted by referral from other national health care centers. The Oncology Center at KAMC was established in 2006 and the lymphoma is treated by the hematology and radiation therapy specialties within the oncology department. All treatment options for Burkitt at different phases of the disease presentation is available including chemotherapy, radiation therapy, surgical oncology, Stem Cell Transplantation and the new targeted therapies. The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board in King Abdullah International Medical Research Center.

The population-based retrospective study included all patients diagnosed with non-Hodgkin Burkitt lymphoma. Also, the study was limited to all adult patients above 18 years-old whom were diagnosed and treated during the period from January 2001 till august 2017 in the Oncology department at King Abdul-Aziz Medical city, Riyadh. All patients that were diagnosed

and treated initially with another type of lymphoma such as Diffuse Large B Cell Lymphoma then shifted to Burkitt lymphoma were excluded. Data collection was done by co-investigators. Medical record numbers and patients' information were derived from the medical records department at King Abdul-Aziz medical city, Riyadh. Patients data were either obtained from electronic medical records at Best Care system, or hard copy files. All demographical variables that were thought to be associated with the outcome of the treatment such as age and gender, were assessed. Co-morbidities included Diabetes mellitus, cardiac disease, renal disease, liver disease, and immunodeficiency. Initial lab investigations at the time of diagnosis including Blood parameters (White Blood Cells, Hemoglobin, Platelets), LDH, creatinine, and liver function tests (AST, ALT, Bilirubin, ALK and Albumin) were collected. Radiological reports were used to assess the spread of the disease in Neck, chest, abdomen, pelvis. Pathological variables were assessed such as the location of the biopsy, stage of the disease, and cytogenicity of the disease. Patients of different treatment regimens that were used to treat Burkitt including hyper-CVAD, CHOP and Magrath were described in the data sheet. Many studies showed that the use of Rituximab alongside with the chemotherapy has an effect on the overall survival outcome therefore it was added to the variables. Mortality incidence among our population was studied.

All data were collected at first in paper sheets than entered in Microsoft Excel sheet. Co-investigators were responsible of the whole process of extracting

and entering the data. Confidentiality agreement of all patients' information was signed by all investigators.

Statistical analysis of the data was done by Co-investigators using SPSS, version 20. Categorical variables were described by percentages and frequencies. The relation between descriptive variables and mortality was calculated by Fishers exact test due to the small sample size. Numerical variables were described by mean and standard deviation. All variables of clinical importance were included despite their statistical analysis. Initially Logistic regression was set to identify risk factors and comorbidities associated with increased mortality. However due to the small sample size it was not applicable. Kaplan Meier survival analysis was used for simple survival analysis. Odds ratios with 95% confidence interval were reported. P value equal or less than 5% or 0.05 was considered statically significant.

RESULTS:

Over the last fifteen years 13 adult patients were treated with the first line regimen in King Abdul-Aziz Medical City in Riyadh were all included in this study. 12 of whom (91.7%) were Saudis. The minimum age was 18 years old and the maximum age was 81 years old with the mean age of 64.69. 46.2% of the sample size were male patients. 4 patients (30.8%) have bone marrow involvement and Central nerves system involvement was (8.3%) with one patient only. 5 patients (41.7%) showed tumor lysis syndrome and 3 patients (23.1%) showed B symptoms.

Table 1 Presented the sample characteristics of Burkitt Lymphoma patients in King Abdulaziz Medical City, Riyadh by percentages

Sample Characteristics	Number	Percentage
Gender (Male)	6	46.2%
Nationality (Saudi)	12	91.7%
Bone Marrow Involvement	4	30.8%
CNS Involvement	1	8.3%
Tumor Lysis	5	41.7%
B symptoms	3	23.1%

The variables that show significance were bone marrow involvement with P value of 0.014 and tumor lysis syndrome with P value of 0.045. Other variables such as Central nervous system involvement with a P

value of 1, B symptoms with a P value of 0.528, WBC of more than $11.0 \times 10^9/L$ with a P value of 1, and LDH of more than $> 250 U/L$ with a P value of 0.528 were all insignificant in this study.

Table 2 presented the odds ratio and P value of each variable in coloration with mortality

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence interval		P value
		Lower	Upper	
Age > 55	3.333	0.762	14.576	0.203
Bone Marrow Involvement	10	1.558	64.2	0.014
CNS Involvement	1.11	0.904	1.366	1
Tumor Lysis	4.5	1.32	15.27	0.045
B Symptoms	1.43	0.952	2.143	0.528
WBC > $11.0 \times 10^9/L$	1.67	0.22	12.6	1
LDH > 250 U/L	1.429	0.952	2.143	0.528

The outcome mortality rate of this study with the first line regimen was 3 out of 13 (23%) with deaths occurring within the first two months of the treatment.

Table 3 presented the survival rate of Burkitt Lymphoma patients whom been treated with Hyper-CVAD and Rituximab at King Abdulaziz Medical City, Riyadh.

DISCUSSION:

As mentioned earlier our research compares the survival rate and outcomes of our treatment of Burkitt lymphoma to other regimens that are being used in different institutes. By comparing the results, it helps us to identify the most significant factors that contribute to the mortality and morbidity of Burkitt lymphoma. There are two studies that we found appropriate one of the studies used similar chemotherapy regimen as King Abdul-Aziz medical City which was combination of Hyper-CVAD and Rituximab. The other study compared four types of regimen which are BFM, CODOX/M-IVAC, hyper-CVAD, and CHOP/CHOEP. There are many factors

that we collected for example blood parameters and liver enzymes. However the most important factors that we found significant in literatures are age above 55, bone marrow involvement, central nervous system involvement, tumor lysis syndrome, B symptoms (fever, night sweats, and weight loss), WBC > $11.0 \times 10^9/L$ and LDH > 250 U/L. Out of these factors in our study we found that bone marrow involvement and tumor lysis syndrome were significant factor affecting the mortality, and the P value for them were 0.014 for bone marrow involvement and a P value of 0.045 for tumor lysis syndrome. Comparing to the two studies the bone marrow was significant in one with a P value of less than 0.0001.[7] unlike our study the central

nervous system was significant in both with a p value of 0.02 and 0.065.[7,8] And similarly to our study one study found that LDH > 250 U/L was found insignificant with a p value of 0.464.[8] However the other study showed significant with a p value of 0.0006.[7] in respect of age above 55 comparing to age below 55, it was found in one study as a remarkable contributor for a higher death rate (2% vs 11%; P = .0002).[7] nonetheless neither in our study nor the other study that compared to the age had any importance with a p value of 0.784 in the compared study.[8] In regards to the tumor lysis syndrome, it had a significance in our study. Yet, there are no studies that looked for the significance of it. This factor that no study mentioned could be an eye opener for the hematology/oncology community, since it played a role in the mortality rate of our subjects. Adjusting and early recognition of this factor could help if further research is conducted to lower the mortality rate. The total survival rate of our study was 77%, nevertheless who ever survived the first two months had a survival rate up to 100%. The survival rate of the two studies were 80% and 69%. [7,8] Together with the survival rate of our study, we could come in conclusion that the regiment that is being used in king Abdul-Aziz Medical City showed close survival rate to other studies done in other institutes.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, Burkitt lymphoma patients have good prognosis as being showed in the discussion regardless of the conflicting variables that contributed to the mortality. The majority of the mortality rate happens in the first two months. And the only two significant factors are bone marrow involvement and tumor lysis syndrome. Since our sample size was small, we recommend a collaborative work with other oncology institutes in Saudi Arabia for data collection and analysis.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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